

Survey results (October 2022)

1) How old are you ?		
Answers	Number of answers	Number of answers in %
15-24	344	10%
25-34	964	28%
35-44	792	23%
45-54	585	17%
55-64	516	15%
65-74	138	4%
75-85	103	3%
Total	3442	100%

2) To which gender do you identify?		
Answers	Number of answers	Number of answers in %
Male	1687	49%
Female	1652	48%
Other	0	0%
Prefer not to say	103	3%
Total	3442	100%

3) What is your ethnicity ?		
Answers	Number of answers	Number of answers in %
Asian	138	4%
Black or African American	241	7%
White European	2754	84%
Other	171	5%
Prefer not to say	138	4%
Total	3442	100%

4) Where do you live?		
Answers	Number of answers	Number of answers in %
Czech Republic	312	9,1%
France	403	11,7%
Germany	374	10,9%
Hungary	297	8,6%
Italy	163	4,7%
Spain	515	15,0%
The Netherlands	306	8,9%
United Kingdom	504	14,6%
Other EU country	402	11,7%
Other country	166	4,8%
Total	3442	100,00%

5) What is your level of education?		
Answers	Number of answers	Number of answers in %
Primary School/Technician/Apprentice	172	5%
Secondary School/High School Diploma/Technologist	688	20%
Bachelors Level Graduate Degree	929	27%
Masters or other Post Graduate Degree	1170	34%
Doctorate Degree	482	14%
Total	3442	100%

6) : Are you aware of plastic pollution and the impact it has on the environment ?		
Answers	Number of answers	Number of answers in %
yes	3235	94%
no	103	3%
Aware but don't know the impact	103	3%
Total	3442	100%

7) Do you think that plastic pollution affects you or just the environment?		
Answers	Number of answers	Number of answers in %
Affects me and the environment	3235	94%
Just the environment	138	4%
Don't know	69	2%
Total	3442	100%

8) Do you know what happens to plastic waste?		
Answers	Number of answers	Number of answers in %
It is a biodegradable material so it eventually disintegrates	69	2%
It never fully goes away; it just breaks into little pieces	792	23%
There is no such thing as plastic waste, all plastic is recycled	34	1%
Part of it is recycled, the rest goes into landfill or pollutes the environment	2168	63%
It is dumped in rivers, lakes and the sea	275	8%
I don't know what happens to it	103	3%
Total	3442	100%

9) Where does the majority of European plastic waste end up?		
Answers	Number of answers	Number of answers in %
Rivers and oceans	757	22%
Burned for energy	482	14%
Landfill	1480	43%
Recycled	688	20%
Don't know	34	1%
Total	3442	100%

10) Do you help at all with reducing plastic pollution?		
Answers	Number of answers	Number of answers in %
I help a lot	826	24%
I help a little	2306	67%
I don't help	34	1%
I would like to help but don't know how	275	8%
Total	3442	100%

11) Is there much plastic pollution around where you live?		
Answers	Number of answers	Number of answers in %
A lot	379	11%
A moderate amount	1239	36%
A little	1239	36%
None at all	69	2%
Don't know	516	15%
Total	3442	100%

12) Do you think that your government is doing enough to address plastic pollution?		
Answers	Number of answers	Number of answers in %
Yes, they are doing enough	344	10%
No, they aren't doing enough	2582	75%
Don't know	516	15%
Total	3442	100%

13) Do you know if plastic medicine blister packs are recyclable using normal recycling methods?		
Answers	Number of answers	Number of answers in %
Yes	757	22%
No	2685	78%
Total	3442	100%

14) What share of medicine blister packs do you think are recycled at the moment?		
Answers	Number of answers	Number of answers in %
Not recycled	929	27%
0 to 25%	2306	67%
26 to 50%	34	1%
51 to 75%	138	4%
76 to 100%	34	1%
Total	3442	100%

15) Would you like to see plastic medicine blister packs replaced with a more environmentally friendly alternative packaging approach?		
Answers	Number of answers	Number of answers in %
No	103	3%
Yes, as long as the cost didn't increase	1446	42%
Yes, as long as the cost increase was no more than 20%	998	29%
Yes, along as the cost increase was no more than 50%	172	5%
Yes, I am not concerned about the additional cost.	723	21%
Total	3442	100%

16) Would you be willing to recycle your plastic blister packs via a suitable scheme?		
Answers	Number of answers	Number of answers in %
No	3373	98%
Yes	69	2%
Total	3442	100%

17) Would you be willing to drop off blister packs at your local pharmacy for recycling?		
Answers	Number	Number in %
Yes	3132	91%
No	310	9%
Total	3442	100%

18) Would you agree with increasing taxes to encourage the recycling of more medicine packaging?		
Answers	Number of answers	Number of answers in %
Yes	1687	49%
No	1755	51%
Total	3442	100%

19) Would you support a deposit scheme to encourage recycling of medicines and packaging ? A refund would be given when the unused medicine and packaging is returned for recycling.		
Answers	Number of answers	Number of answers in %
Yes	3235	94%
No	207	6%
Total	3442	100%

20) Would you prefer the use of biodegradable (compostable) food packaging over the use of traditional fast-food packaging?		
Answers	Number of answers	Number of answers in %
No	275	8%
Yes, as long as the cost didn't increase	620	18%
Yes, as long as there was no impact on the food lifetime	1205	35%
Yes, as long as the cost increase was no more than 10%	413	12%
Yes, along as the cost increase was no more than 20%	207	6%
Yes, I am not concerned about the additional cost.	723	21%
Total	3442	100%

21) Would you be willing to pay a little more for environmentally sustainable food packaging.		
Answers	Number of answers	Number of answers in %
Yes	2754	80%
No	688	20%
Total	3442	200%

22) How effective do you believe recycling is in preventing plastic multilayer food packaging waste?		
Answers	Number of answers	Number of answers in %
Very effective	826	24%
Somewhat effective	1687	49%
Not very effective	929	27%
Total	3442	100%

23) What reasons would discourage you from recycling food packaging? Please tick all that apply.		
Answers	Number of answers	Number of answers in %
Unsure how to recycle	1446	42%
Don't have time	275	8%
Not important	69	2%
No access to recycling facilities	1652	48%
Total	3442	100%

24) Would you like to see plastic-free aisles in shops/supermarkets?		
Answers	Number of answers	Number of answers in %
Yes	2478	72%
No	964	28%
Total	3442	100%

25) Do you look at food packaging to see if it can be recycled?		
Answers	Number of answers	Number of answers in %
Yes	2168	63%
No	1274	37%
Total	3442	100%

26) Would you support the introduction of tax/surcharge system to encourage the recycling of more food packaging?		
Answers	Number of answers	Number of answers in %
Yes	2134	62%
No	1308	38%
Total	3442	100%

27) We use too much plastic; alternatives should be used where possible.		
Answers	Number of answers	Number of answers in %
Agree	2960	86%
Disagree	172	5%
Neither agree or disagree	310	9%
Total	3442	100%

28) Europe must take urgent action to protect the environment and reduce the amounts of plastic waste and waste mismanagement.		
Answers	Number of answers	Number of answers in %
Agree	3098	90%
Disagree	138	4%
Neither agree or disagree	207	6%
Total	3442	100%

29) I would be willing to pay more for alternatives to current plastic packaging.		
Answers	Number of answers	Number of answers in %
Agree	1618	47%
Disagree	826	24%
Neither agree or disagree	998	29%
Total	3442	100%

30) There should be stricter legislation to ensure more plastic is recycled.		
Answers	Number of answers	Number of answers in %
Agree	3201	93%
Disagree	69	2%
Neither agree or disagree	172	5%
Total	3442	100%

